

5 G technology millimeter waves could induce Coronavirus (COVID-19) within a biological cell

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Abstract: A DNA is built from charged electrons and atoms and has the inductor-like structure. This structure could be divided into linear, toroid and round inductors. These inductors interact with external electromagnetic waves, move and produce some extra waves within the cells. The shapes of these waves are similar to shapes of hexagonal and pentagonal bases of their DNA source. These waves produce some holes in liquid within the nucleus and cells. To fill these holes, some extra hexagonal and pentagonal bases are produced. These bases could join to each other and form some viruses like Coronavirus. To produce these viruses within a cell, its need that wavelength of external waves be shorter than the size of cell. Thus 5G millimeter waves could be good candidates for applying in creating COVID-19 and Coronaviruses within biological cells..

Keywords: COVID-19, 5G technology, Millimeter wave, DNA, Inductor

I.Introduction:

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is the main problem in this year that involve with all people in the world (Baud et al, 2020). This is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Totally, this virus is a member of related viruses that cause diseases in mammals and birds. In humans, coronaviruses cause respiratory tract infections that can be mild, such as some cases of the common cold (among other possible causes, predominantly rhinoviruses), and others that can be lethal, such as SARS, MERS, and COVID-19. Among them, COVID-19 is an enveloped viruses with a positive-sense single-stranded RNA genome and a nucleocapsid of helical symmetry. The genome size of coronaviruses ranges from approximately 27 to 34 kilobases, the largest among known RNA viruses (Sexton et al., 2016; Fehr et al., 2015). Until now, many scientists have tried to find method to cure this disease (Wang et al., 2020; Hui et al., 2020); however, they don't succeed.

Newly, a question arises that is there any relation between 5G technology and COVID-19? The 5G technology is the fifth-generation mobile technology which its frequency spectrum could be divided into millimeter waves, mid-band, and low-band. Low-band uses a similar frequency range as the predecessor, 4G. 5G

millimeter wave is the fastest, with actual speeds often being 1–2 Gbit/s down. Its frequencies are above 24 GHz, reaching up to 72 GHz, which is above the extremely high frequency band's lower boundary. Millimeter waves have shorter range than microwaves, therefore the cells are limited to smaller size (Rappaport et al, 2013; Nordrum et al, 2019; Saracco, 2019). Consequently, biological cells also could act like a receiver for these waves. Many researchers have considered the effects of 5G technology on the human's health. For example, it has been shown that 5G mobile networking technology will affect not only the skin and eyes, but will have adverse systemic effects as well (Kostoff et al, 2020). In another research, it has been argued that 5G technologies cause many harms to human health. Cancer is only one problem, and one that is easily solved. 5G cause 720! (factorial) different maladies in human beings, and can kill everything that lives but some forms of micro organisms (Christianto et al, 2019). To consider the effects of 5G millimeter waves on biological systems, we should propose a model which describes the process of exchanging waves between 5G towers and host cells.

Up to date, some researchers have tried to propose a model for using of waves in extracting information within cells (Jr. et al. 2020; Baluška and Jr, 2018). These waves could be transverse electromagnetic fields or longitudinal ultrasound waves. A DNA is built from charged particles and according to laws of physics, by any

motion of these particles, some electromagnetic waves are emerged (Rattemeyer et al, 1981). Also, the structure of a DNA is similar to the structure of an inductor (Sepehri, 2017) in a receiver and can produce some waves. Thus, a DNA could emit some waves and interact with external waves. However, most of waves have a length more than the size of cells and pass then without any effect. Only, limited waves with lengths smaller than millimeter could penetrate into cell membrane and interact with DNA inductors. These wavelengths could be observed in 5 G technology. Thus, towers in this technology could exchange waves with DNAs within cells and produce various types of diseases like COVID-19. In this research, we propose a mechanism for exchanged waves between towers and host cells and obtain effective wavelengths.

The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, we propose a mechanism for exchanging waves between towers and cells in 5G technology. In section III, we calculate the effective wavelengths for producing COVID-19 in 5 G technology. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Method: A mechanism for exchanging waves between towers and cells in 5G technology

A DNA is built from atoms and electrons. These particles have some electrical charges and emit electrical fields. Also, by each motion of a DNA, its atoms and electrons move. According to laws of physics, by motion of charged particles, some magnetic waves are emerged. Consequently, a DNA emits both electrical and magnetic fields and play the role of electrical devices within a cell. The structure of a DNA within a cell is similar to the structure of an inductor. When a DNA coils around a nucleosome, it takes the shape of a toroid inductor. Also, by coiling around another axes, a DNA becomes very similar to round inductors. (See figure 1). A DNA coils several times around different axes within chromosomes and produces different types of inductors and electronic devices. Thus, any state of a DNA is similar to a type of an inductor and emits an special wave. Some of these waves are linear, some are curved and some others have toroidal shapes (See figure 2).

Fig 1: A similarity between different states of DNA with different types of inductors

Fig 2: A DNA within the nucleus acts like the inductors and emit magnetic waves

A DNA as an electronic device within a cell could exchange waves with medium. Specially, when an electromagnetic wave pass the cell membrane and the nuclear membrane, induces an extra magnetic field within the DNA inductor and interacts with its fields. This interaction causes to extra motions of this DNA. By motion of this DNA, its charges move and emit electromagnetic waves. Wavelength of emitted waves from a DNA is equal or less than its size within a cell . Also, shapes of radiated waves by a DNA have direct relations with the shapes of their genetic source. A DNA is formed from hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds. Thus,

its emitted waves have hexagonal and pentagonal shapes. These waves produce some hexagonal and pentagonal holes within the liquids of a nucleus and a cell. To fill these holes, some hexagonal and pentagonal molecules are built. These extra hexagonal and pentagonal bases may join to each other and form some structures like RNAs of COVID-19 viruses. To produce these viruses, it's needed that wavelengths of external electromagnetic fields be equal or less than size of a cell. For this reason, 5G technology waves could have the main role in the emergence of COVID-19, however radio waves couldn't have any effect on the evolutions within a cell (See Figure 3).

Fig 3: 5 G technology waves could pass the cell membranes and cause to production of COVID-19. however radio waves stop

III. Results: Effective wavelengths within a cell in 5G technology

Now, we propose a model to obtain a probability for the amount of effects of external fields on the evolutions of cells within a cell. This probability is related to number of microstates of a DNA within a cell:

$$P_{DNA} = \Omega_{DNA, EM} / \Omega_{DNA, tot} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{DNA} is the probability, $\Omega_{DNA, EM}$ is number of microstates which are produced by the interaction between DNAs and electromagnetic waves and $\Omega_{DNA, tot}$ is total number of microstates. These microstates have direct relations with entropies:

$$S_{DNA} = K_S \text{ LOG } (\Omega_{DNA, EM}) \quad (2)$$

Where S_{DNA} is the entropy and K_S is a constant. On the other hand, entropies have direct relations with energies:

$$S_{DNA} = E_{DNA} / T_{cell} \quad (3)$$

Where E_{DNA} is the excited energy of a DNA and T_{cell} is the temperature within a cell. Excited energy of a DNA depends on the linear and curved energies of hexagonal and pentagonal bases:

$$E_{DNA} = U_{B, linear,5} V_{B, linear,5} + U_{B, curved,5} V_{B, curved,5} + U_{B, supercoil,5} V_{B, supercoil,5} +$$

$$U_{B, \text{linear},6} V_{B, \text{linear},6} + U_{B, \text{curved},6} V_{B, \text{curved},6} + U_{B, \text{supercoil},6} V_{B, \text{supercoil},6} \quad (4)$$

Where $U_{B, \text{linear},5/6}$ is the energy density of a pentagonal/hexagonal molecule, $V_{B, \text{linear}, ,5/6}$ is the volume of a pentagonal/hexagonal disk , $U_{B, \text{curved}, ,5/6}$ is the energy density of a pentagonal/hexagonal molecule which coils around a nucleosome, $V_{B, \text{curved}, ,5/6}$ is the volume of a coiled pentagonal/hexagonal disk, $U_{B, \text{supercoil}, ,5/6}$ is the energy density of a pentagonal/hexagonal molecule which is coils around supercoil axes and $V_{B, \text{supercoil}, ,5/6}$ is its volume. Volumes can be obtained from below equations:

$$V_{B, \text{linear},5} = 5 [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] [r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}]$$

$$V_{B, \text{linear},6} = 5 [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})] [r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}]$$

$$V_{B, \text{curved},5} = 5\pi [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] \times$$

$$[r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}] [r_{\text{histone}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2$$

$$V_{B, \text{curved},6} = 5\pi [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})] \times$$

$$[r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}] [r_{\text{histone}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2$$

$$V_{B, \text{supercoil},5} = 5\pi^2 [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] \times$$

$$[r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}] [r_{\text{histone}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2 [r_{\text{supercoil}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2$$

$$V_{B, \text{supercoil},6} = 5\pi^2 [1/2 (r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})] \times$$

$$[r_{\text{base}} + x_{\text{EM}}][r_{\text{histone}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2[r_{\text{supercoil}} + x_{\text{EM}}]^2 \quad (5)$$

Where r_{base} is the length of a base ($\sim 10^{-9}$), r_{histone} is the radius of histones ($\sim 10^{-8}$), $r_{\text{supercoil}}$ is the radius of a supercoil ($\sim 10^{-7}$), Θ_{hexa} ($\pi/6$) is the central angle of a hexagonal molecule, Θ_{penta} ($\pi/5$) is the central angle of pentagonal molecule, x_{EM} is the oscillating length which has a direct relation with the wavelength of external field:

$$E_{\text{EM}} = 1/2 K_{\text{EM}} x_{\text{EM}}^2 = h \nu_{\text{EM}} = h c / \lambda_{\text{EM}} \quad (6)$$

Where ν_{EM} is the frequency, λ_{EM} is the wavelength of external field, c is the velocity of light and h is the plank constant. Thus, we can write below equation:

$$x_{\text{EM}} \sim \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2} \quad (7)$$

Now, we should calculate magnetic energies and magnetic fields. We assume that a DNA acts like an inductor and thus, we write below equation for its magnetic fields:

For linear inductor:

$$B_{\text{DNA, linear, 5/6}} = \mu_0 n_{\text{gene 5/6}} I_{\text{gene, 5/6}} \quad (8)$$

For curved inductor:

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, curved,5/6}} = \mu_0 \mathbf{n}_{\text{gene5/6}} \mathbf{I}_{\text{gene,5/6}} / 2\pi [r_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] \quad (9)$$

For supercoils:

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, curved,5/6}} = \mu_0 \mathbf{n}_{\text{gene5/6}} \mathbf{I}_{\text{gene,5/6}} / [4\pi^2 [r_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] [r_{\text{supercoil}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]] \quad (10)$$

Where $n_{\text{gene5/6}}$ is the density of genes including hexagonal and pentagonal molecules (Redon et al., 2006) within DNAs, r_{histone} is the size of histone (3×10^{-10}) (Allfrey et al, 1964), $r_{\text{supercoil}}$ is the radius of supercoil ($\sim 10^{-9}$) and $I_{\text{gene,5/6}}$ is current which moves along pentagonal/hexagonal molecules of genes. We assume that each gene is in fact a long wire that is coiled around the axis of a DNA. A DNA may have 50000 or more gene (N_{gene}) (Redon et al., 2006) and each gene has around 10^{-12} meter long (L_{gene}) within a cell. Thus, we can calculate density of genes (n_{gene}):

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = \mathbf{N}_{\text{gene}} / \mathbf{L}_{\text{gene5/6}} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{\text{gene}} = 50000 (\text{Redon et al., 2006}) \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{\text{gene}} = 10^{-12} \text{m} (\text{Dolezel et al, 2003; Greilhuber et al., 2005}) \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = 2 \times 10^{-12} \text{m} (\text{Dolezel et al, 2003; Greilhuber et al., 2005}) \quad (14)$$

$$n_{\text{gene}, 5/6} = 2.5 \times 10^{16} \quad (15)$$

To calculate the value of the current along genes, we should calculate total effective charge of all genes ($Q_{\text{gene},5/6}$) and their velocity ($V_{\text{gene},5/6}$).

$$I_{\text{gene},5/6} = Q_{\text{gene},5/6} V_{\text{gene},5/6} \quad (16)$$

Effective charges of all genes are different from their normal total charges. A gene may have a few normal charges, because its charges cancel the effect of each other in the static state. However, during the gene expression and DNA evolutions, each charge has a separate effect. For this reason, we should regard total charges of all genes. To obtain this charge, we should write:

$$Q_{\text{gene},5/6} = N_{\text{gene},5/6} q_{\text{gene},5/6} \quad (17)$$

Where $N_{\text{gene},5/6} = 2 N_{\text{gene}}$ is the number of genes including pentagonal/hexagonal molecules and $q_{\text{gene},5/6}$ is the effective charge of pentagonal/hexagonal molecules in a gene. Again, we insist that effective charge of a gene is different from its normal charge. In fact, we should regard all electrons and atoms that contribute in gene expression. For this reason, we should write:

$$q_{\text{gene},5/6} = 4N_{\text{base}} q_{\text{base}} \quad (18)$$

where N_{base} is the number of base pairs within a gene (Redon et al., 2006; Allfrey et al, 1964) and q_{base} is the effective electrical charge of a base. We can put approximate numbers and obtain the effective charge of all genes:

$$N_{\text{base}} = 10^9 \text{ (Abecasis et al, 2012; Auton et al, 2015)} \quad (19)$$

$$q_{\text{base}} = (10^{-20}) \quad q_{\text{electron}} = (10^{-20}) \times 1/6 \times 10^{-19} \quad (20)$$

$$Q_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = 4 \times 10^{-4} \quad (21)$$

Now, we calculate the effective velocity of genes:

$$V_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = L_{\text{gene, 5/6}} \omega_{\text{gene, 5/6}} \quad (22)$$

This velocity depends on the length of a gene ($L_{\text{gene, 5/6}}$) and its rotating velocity ($\omega_{\text{gene, 5/6}}$).

$$L_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = 2 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m (Dolezel et al, 2003; Greilhuber, 2005)} \quad (23)$$

The rotating velocity of a gene ($\omega_{\text{gene, 5/6}}$) can be obtained by summing over rotating velocities of all its effective charges ($\omega_{\text{charge, 5/6}}$):

$$\omega_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = n_{\text{charge, 5/6}} \omega_{\text{charge, 5/6}} \quad (24)$$

To obtain number of charges, we multiply number of bases and number of atoms/electrons

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} = 2\mathbf{N}_{\text{base}} \mathbf{N}_{\text{atom}} \quad (25)$$

Now, we put approximate values for numbers and obtain velocity of genes:

$$\mathbf{N}_{\text{base}} = 10^9 \text{ (Abecasis et al, 2012; Auton et al, 2015)} \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{\text{atom}} = 10 \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} = 2 \times 10^{10} \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{\omega}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} = 2\pi/\mathbf{T}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} = [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{1/2} / \mathbf{c} \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{\omega}_{\text{charge, 5/6}} = 6.28 \times 10 \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{\text{gene, 5/6}} = 2.516 \times 10^0 \quad (32)$$

Substituting values of velocity from equation (32) and charges from equation (21) in equation (16), we can obtain the current of genes:

$$\mathbf{I}_{\text{gene, 5/6}} \sim 10^{-3} \quad (33)$$

Putting the current from above equation (33) and density of genes from equation (15) in equations (6-10), we calculate magnetic fields of a DNA within a cell.

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, linear, 5/6}} \sim 10^7 [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-1/2} \quad (34)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, curved,5/6}} \sim 10^{16} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-1} \quad (35)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, supercoil,5/6}} \sim 10^{25} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{3/2} \quad (36)$$

Using these fields, we can obtain energy density of magnetic fields around a DNA within a cell.

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \quad (37)$$

$$U_{\text{B, linear,5/6}} = ([\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, linear,5/6}}]^2 / 2 \mu_0) \sim 10^{21} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-1} \quad (38)$$

$$U_{\text{B, curved,5/6}} = ([\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, curved,5/6}}]^2 / 2 \mu_0) \sim 10^{38} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-2} \quad (39)$$

$$U_{\text{B, supercoil,5/6}} = ([\mathbf{B}_{\text{DNA, supercoil,5/6}}]^2 / 2 \mu_0) \sim 10^{56} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-3} \quad (40)$$

Consequently, substituting above results in equation (4), total energy can be obtained from below equation:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{DNA}} = & [5 [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] \\ & + 5 [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] \times 10^{21} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-1} \\ & + [5\pi [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] \times \\ & [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 \\ & + 5\pi [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})] \times \\ & [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 \times 10^{38} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + [5\pi^2 [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{penta}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{penta}})] \times \\
& [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \mathbf{x}_{\text{EM}}] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 [\mathbf{r}_{\text{supercoil}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 \\
& + 5\pi^2 [1/2 (\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2})^2 \cos(\Theta_{\text{hexa}}) \sin(\Theta_{\text{hexa}})]] \times \\
& [\mathbf{r}_{\text{base}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}] [\mathbf{r}_{\text{histone}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 [\mathbf{r}_{\text{supercoil}} + \lambda_{\text{EM}}^{-1/2}]^2 \times 10^{56} [\lambda_{\text{EM}}]^{-3} \quad (41)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting above equation in equations (1-3), we can obtain the probability for the amount of effects of external fields on the evolutions of cells within a cell:

$$\mathbf{P}_{\text{DNA}} = \exp (\mathbf{K}_S \mathbf{E}_{\text{DNA}} / \mathbf{T}_{\text{cell}}) / \mathbf{\Omega}_{\text{DNA, tot}} \quad (42)$$

Above probability depends on the wavelength of external fields.

In figure 4, we show the probability for producing hexagonal and pentagonal DNA holes within a cell. This figure indicates that by decreasing the wavelength ($< 10^{-3}\text{m}$), waves pass the cell membrane and interact with DNAs. This interaction causes to the motions of DNAs. By motions of DNAs, their charges move and emit some strong waves. These waves produce some hexagonal and pentagonal holes within a cell. To fill these holes some extra bases are produced. These bases could join to each other and form some viruses like COVID-19.

Fig 4: The probability for the effect of waves on the evolutions of a DNA within a cell in terms of wavelength

Summary:

In this research, we have shown that new generation mobile technology like 5G could have the main role in constructing various types of viruses like Coronaviruses within a cell. Some wavelengths in these technologies are smaller

than the size of biological cells and could pass the cell membrane and enter into the nucleus. These waves interact with DNAs and move them. A DNA is formed from charged particles and by its motions, some electromagnetic waves are emerged. These waves produce some hexagonal and pentagonal holes within liquids within nucleus and the cell. To fill these holes, some bases are produced. These bases join to each other and construct Coronaviruses.

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